

Alternative ways of European participatory organic fruit breeding projects

NOVAFRUITS

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The CRA-W and the CRRG institutions

The **Walloon Agricultural Research Centre (CRA-W)** is a Belgian public regional institution developing research programs in agriculture, horticulture and forestry. One of its missions is to safeguard, evaluate and promote the use of the large diversity of its regional fruit tree genetic resources. Besides the direct release of the best performing, most robust and disease tolerant old fruit cultivars via a nursery network, the CRA-W also started, since the late 80s, an apple breeding program using local genetic resources as sources of polygenic disease resistance or tolerance.

The **Centre Régional de Ressources Génétiques (CRRG)**, Villeneuve d'Ascq, France) is part of the Espaces Naturels Régionaux (ENRx) located in the Hauts-de-France area. Its role is to safeguard and promote regional fruit, vegetable and animal genetic resources. In close partnership with CRA-W, the CRRG also manages a breeding program in which local cultivars are used as parents to create more robust cider and dessert apple cultivars.

Since more than 30 years, both CRA-W and CRRG are close partners with a common website (www.biodimestica.eu/fr) and have a formal collaboration agreement for co-breeding and sharing common genetic resources management tools (assessment scales, common database, etc.) and material responsibilities.

The collaboration between these two organizations was also at the origin of the creation of the NOVAFRUITS association, celebrating its 10 years anniversary in 2024. This successful collaboration already allowed for the selection and commercialization of the apple cultivar "Ducasse".

NOVAFRUITS: A trans-border organic participative fruit breeding association based on more robust and disease tolerant old local cultivars.

The primary intention of the NOVAFRUITS association is the participative creation, evaluation and promotion of interesting, more robust and disease tolerant fruit tree cultivars adapted to Wallonia, North France and Normandie. The common goal is to co-develop new organic markets for locally bred fruit cultivars for both fresh high-quality dessert organic fruits but also for processed produces such as juice and apple cider. The breeding programs are focused on the obtention of new cultivars that are better adapted to organic and low input organic farming systems. The selection of cultivars is therefore based on their better robustness, their better tolerance to biotic stresses such as insects and diseases, their long keeping ability, their capacity of adaptation and of course, their good yield, taste and nutrients content.

NOVAFRUITS is a transborder participatory organic fruit breeding association. The initiative to create such an association was mostly based on the friendship between a few innovative fruit growers and the dynamic breeders from both public institutions (CRA-W and CRRG).

The breeding program started in 1988 at the CRA-W and few years later at the CRRG by using old best performing varieties as a source of robustness and polygenic disease tolerance. A distinctive feature of this breeding program is that both regional institutes based their choices of crosses on the long-term evaluation process of their large regional collections in specific non-sprayed experimental orchards. This absence of treatment allows to highlight the real capacity of adaptation and robustness of each cultivar in challenging unsprayed conditions.

NOVAFRUITS currently gathers 33 organic apple and pear growers from Wallonia (Belgium) and Northern France (both Normandie and Hauts de France) as well as two regional public institutes – the CRA-W and the CRRG - and four regional extension services (Chambre de l'Agriculture, GAWI-Bio, Bio des Hauts de France, Association Domaine de Merval). Its members are integrated in the association after a formal demand which is evaluated by the management board, mostly based on the condition that growers have organic certification on their entire fruit productions. Close interactions with consumers are promoted by most growers which are valorizing such new elite cultivars in short marketing circuits.

InnOBreed collaboration

Since 2022, NOVAFRUITS is part of the Horizon Europe project InnOBreed as a case study, joining a network of European colleagues working in the same field.

NOVAFRUITS is a European pioneer regarding regional participative organic pome fruit breeding. As an historical case study, NOVAFRUITS activities act as an inspiring example for innovative methods, tools, available genetic resources and pre-breeding material, but also for the socio-economic aspects.

The InnOBreed project is creating dynamic participative research activities, interactions and exchange of ideas, protocols and expertise between project partners, other case studies and stakeholders. It will create synergies and collaborative improvements for the whole community of fruit genetic resources managers, breeders and variety testers dealing with lower input organic production in Europe.

Thanks to the InnOBreed project, stronger collaborative and complementary activities between case studies will be implemented through Europe.

You can find more information about NOVAFRUITS here:
<https://biodimestica.eu/fr>

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